

A Study on Perception of Customers towards Modern Banking Services of Public Sector Banks with Special Reference to Kanyakumari District

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 3

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Andrews Scott, D. “A Study on Perception of Customers towards Modern Banking Services of Public Sector Banks with Special Reference to Kanyakumari District.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S3, 2019, pp. 49–55.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572419>

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Abstract

The present study is confined within a precise modern banking services which have been mostly used by the customers i.e. Automatic Teller Machine (ATM), Tele Banking, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, Credit card, Debit card, Electronic Clearing Service (ECS), National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT), Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS), Cheque Truncation System (CTS), Dematerialisation. The research is based on data collected from customers of select public sector banks in Kanyakumari district. Other aspects of bank and banking services are not considered in this study. Primary data were collected through interview schedule distributed to the customers for the purpose of extracting the required data. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to collect details on perception of customers regarding the modern banking services in Kanyakumari district. 150 sample respondents have been selected from public sector banks for the study. The banking sector plays a vital role in the field of providing modern banking services to their customers. The benefit of the modern banking services with all its modern technology and ultimate development must be extended to each and every citizen in every nook and corner of the nation. The public sector banks provide many modern banking services throughout the country.

Keywords: Modern Banking Services, Public Sector Banks, Mobile Banking and Electronic Clearing Service

Introduction

Modern Banking is the most inventive services offered by the banks. The transformation from traditional banking to modern banking has been a dramatic change. In the days, when technology serves the bank customers through ATMs, Credit cards, Internet banking, Mobile, Tele banking, RTGS, DEMAT and ECS and many more where online banking turned the banks to be fully automatic and hence decline the customer visit to the banks. More and more customers are now using e-delivery channels, which have come to be associated with modern banking services.

Statement of the Problem

There are several major challenges and issues facing the modern banking today. First and perhaps the most important is the security concern. Customers are certainly concerned of giving their bank account number online or paying an invoice through internet. The modern banking services are provided by public sector banks obviously the range of services and the quality of the same differ from other banks. Hence, the researcher has undertaken this study to examine the perception of customers towards modern banking services of public sector banks in Kanyakumari district.

Objectives of the Study

- To identify the opinion of customers regarding modern banking services of public sector banks in Kanyakumari district.
- To identify the problems faced by customers in modern banking services of public sector banks in Kanyakumari district.

Scope of the Study

The present study is confined within a precise modern banking services which have been mostly used by the customers i.e. Automatic Teller Machine (ATM), Tele Banking, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, Credit card, Debit card, Electronic Clearing Service (ECS), National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT), Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS), Cheque Truncation System (CTS), Dematerialisation. The research is based on data collected from customers of select public sector banks in Kanyakumari district. Other aspects of bank and banking services are not considered in this study.

Methodology

Primary data were collected through interview schedule distributed to the customers for the purpose of extracting the required data. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to collect details on perception of customers regarding the modern banking services in Kanyakumari district. 150 sample respondents have been selected from public sector banks for the study.

Limitations of the Study

- The customers were selected for the present study of modern banking services of the public sector banks only. As a result, the generalization of the findings of the present research should be considered carefully. Furthermore, the sample was restricted to public sector banks only.
- The study is restricted to the modern banking services such as Automatic Teller Machine, Debit Card and Credit Card, Tele-Banking, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, National Electronic Fund Transfer, Real Time Gross Settlement, Electronic Clearing Service, Cheque Truncation System and Dematerialisation. The other modern banking services are not considered in this study.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1
Opinion of the Respondents about Electronic Clearing Services

Sl. No.	Electronic Clearing Services	Total Score	Average Score	Rank
1.	ECS-Credit helps fast payment of interest/dividend to the shareholders	8141	54.27	IV
2.	ECS-Credit is very popular for crediting salaries and pension	8534	56.89	III

3.	ECS-Credit used for vender payment	4542	30.28	X
4.	ECS-Credit used for payment of cheques	5286	35.24	IX
5.	ECS-Credit used for payment of bills	9180	61.20	I
6.	ECS-debit helps fast collection of bills	8967	59.78	II
7.	ECS-debit used for collection of insurance premium	7680	51.20	V
8.	ECS-debit helps to recharge mobile phone	7319	48.79	VI
9.	ECS-debit used for collection of cheques	6032	40.21	VIII
10.	ECS-debit used for collection of periodical installments	6747	44.98	VII

Source: Primary data

It is seen from the result obtained through Garret ranking ECS-Credit used for payment of bills ranks first with the mean score of 61.20 which is followed by ECS-debit helps fast collection of bills (59.78), ECS-Credit is very popular for crediting salaries and pension ranks third with the mean score of 56.89 and ECS-Credit used for vender payment ranks last with the mean score of 30.28.

Table 2
Opinion of the Respondents about Electronic Fund Transfer Services

Sl. No.	Electronic Fund Transfer Services	Total Score	Average Score	Rank
1.	Pay is deposited straight into an employee's bank account	7851	52.34	IV
2.	Funds are transferred electronically from one bank account to the billing bank account	5843	38.95	VIII
3.	EFT include reduced administrative cost	6638	44.25	VI
4.	EFT has simplified book keeping	9056	60.37	II
5.	EFT benefits increased efficiency	4823	32.15	IX
6.	EFT has greater security	7277	48.51	V
7.	EFT helps the cardholders make use of a payment card	8678	57.85	III
8.	Direct debit payments from customer to businessman	6185	41.23	VII

9.	Cardholders deposits funds to their own accounts	9533	63.55	I
10.	EFT used for linked accounts enquiry	3867	25.78	X

Source: Primary data

It is seen from the result obtained through Garret ranking Cardholders deposits funds to their own accounts ranks first with the mean score of 63.55 which is followed by EFT has simplified book keeping (60.37), EFT helps the cardholders make use of a payment card ranks third with the mean score of 57.85 and EFT used for linked accounts enquiry ranks last with the mean score of 25.78.

Table 3
Opinion of the Respondents about Real Time Gross Settlement Services

Sl. No.	Real Time Gross Settlement Services	Total Score	Average Score	Rank
1.	RTGS is a large value funds transfer system	8451	56.34	II
2.	RTGS is primarily for large value transactions	8978	59.85	I
3.	RTGS increases velocity of fund flow	6327	42.18	VI
4.	RTGS reduces credit risk	6632	44.21	V
5.	RTGS increases transparency of payments	5873	39.15	VII
6.	RTGS have minimum limit and there is no maximum limit for fund transfer	7845	52.30	III
7.	RTGS takes care of urgent or time critical payments	7482	49.88	IV
8.	Transactions support inter-bank payments	5294	35.29	VIII
9.	Transactions support customer payment	3023	20.15	XI
10.	Transactions support own account transfers	4688	31.25	IX
11.	Transactions support net clearing	4040	26.93	X

Source: Primary data

It is seen from the result obtained through Garret ranking RTGS is primarily for large value transactions ranks first with the mean score of 59.85 which is followed by RTGS is a large value funds transfer system (56.34), RTGS have minimum limit and there is no maximum limit for fund transfer ranks third with the mean score of 52.30 and transactions support customer payment ranks last with the mean score of 20.15.

Table 4
Opinion of the respondents about the different aspects of e-channel services

Sl. No	E-channel services	Total Score	Average Score	Rank
1.	E-channels ensure privacy	8300	55.33	VI
2.	E-channels ensure more transparency	8633	57.55	V
3.	E-channels create more confusion for customers	7836	52.24	VII
4.	E-channels have bright future in global age	7533	50.22	VIII
5.	E-channels improve the quality of customer service in banks	9191	61.27	III
6.	E-channels are necessary in the competitive global and new economy of India	8985	59.90	IV
7.	E-channels make online purchase of goods and services easier	5933	39.55	XII
8.	E-channels create more social relations among the bank employees	6183	41.22	XI
9.	E-channels fulfill all the requirements in time	9689	64.59	I
10.	E-channels charge more hidden cost	6795	45.30	X
11.	More formalities are required to get e-channels issued from the banks	7178	47.85	IX
12.	Online banking helps to manage information in banks more efficiently	9327	62.18	II
13.	Smart card sometime creates technical hurdles to make payments	3509	23.39	XVI
14.	Effecting business transactions in a flexible manner	4992	33.28	XIV
15.	Minimum human intervention	4533	30.22	XV
16.	Quick processing of transactions	5316	35.44	XIII

Source: Primary data

It is seen from the result obtained through Garret ranking E-channels fulfill all the requirements in time ranks first with the mean score of 64.59 which is followed by online banking helps to manage information in banks more efficiently (62.18), E-channels improve the quality of customer service in banks ranks third with the mean score of 61.27 and smart card sometime creates technical hurdles to make payments ranks last with the mean score of 23.39.

Table 5
Problems Faced While Using Technology in Banking System

Sl. No.	Problems	Total Score	Average Score	Rank
1.	Inadequate knowledge	8984	59.89	I
2.	Lack of infrastructure	5037	33.58	VIII
3.	Unsuitable location of ATMs	7853	52.35	III
4.	Number of ATMs insufficient	4313	28.75	IX
5.	Poor network	8345	55.63	II
6.	Time consuming	7479	49.86	IV
7.	Closing of ATM for maintenance	6447	42.98	VI
8.	Closing of ATM for arrangement of cash	5993	39.95	VII
9.	Plastic card blocked by ATMs	6867	45.78	V

Source: Primary data

It is seen from the result obtained through Garret ranking Inadequate knowledge ranks first with the mean score of 59.89 which is followed by Poor network (55.63), Unsuitable location of ATMs ranks third with the mean score of 52.35 and number of ATMs insufficient ranks last with the mean score of 28.75.

Suggestions

Customers should be imparted proper information and training on utilizing the services of modern banking. It is found that customers of the bank use the ATM card only for the purpose of withdrawing of cash only. It is also suggested that the bank shall encourage the customers to use the cards for different purposes like payment of electricity bills, telephone bills, payment of insurance premium and payment for railway and air tickets and so on.

Care should be taken that ATMs should work properly and should be kept in good condition. Further, proper care should be taken for the maintenance of servers in ATM locations which will avoid waiting of customers for a long time.

As a majority of the respondents are uncomfortable in using mobile devices for banking purpose, the banks should form a separate department in the bank itself to take care of the mobile banking services.

Conclusion

The banking sector plays a vital role in the field of providing modern banking services to their customers. The benefit of the modern banking services with all its modern technology and

ultimate development must be extended to each and every citizen in every nook and corner of the nation. The public sector banks provide many modern banking services throughout the country. The customers are the strong pillars supporting the services in any field and the ultimate cause of its success. Therefore, a public sector bank has to concentrate to widen its customer's base to strengthen its activities and achieve success through them by true, sincere and excellent services. In order to have a large number of customers, the public sector banks have to expand its services in villages and towns. It has created an effective distribution channel. The first achievement of public service provider is to survive in the market among many powerful competitors and admits a big competition. The objective of the public service providers must be to serve the public along with its profit motive. In order to survive in the competitive world, public sector banks have provided a variety of services which are beneficial to all types of customers. Customers' satisfaction must be given top priority by the public service providers.

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